

Table 1. The rearing systems observed among the 26 farms included in the study

Rasing systems	Number of farms (26)
Individual pasture	9/26
Collective pasture	9/26
Tropical facilities	4/26
Cages	2/26
Mixed	2/26

Table 2. The calving rearing systems observed among the cows categories and the distribution in quartiles 1,2 and 3.

Cow category	Lactating cows	Dry Cows	Pre-parturient cows	Quatile 1	Quatile 2	Quatile 3
Indoors system	38,5% (10/26)	0%	0%	14%	15%	71%
Pasture system	0%	92% (24/26)	92% (24/26)	0%	16%	12%
Mixed housing systems (Indoor and pasture)	61,5% (16/26)	8% (2/26)	8% (2/26)	86%	69%	17%

Table 3. Classification of calf rearing system across 26 farms stratified into quartiles 1, 2, and 3.

Holdings rearing	Quartile 1	Quartile 2	Quartile 3
Cages	14%	0%	17%
Common grazing	14%	54%	17%
Individual pastures	28%	31%	50%
Tropical rearing system	28%	15%	0%
Mixed	14%	0%	17%

Table 4. Characterization of calf management across the 26 farms included in the study.

	Quartile 1	Quartile 2	Quartile 3
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Colostrum provision			
Colostrum (bottle 2 to 3 lit per animal)	57%	15%	83%
Suckling calves from the mother (not knowing the amount)	43%	85%	17%
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Colostrum management			
Provided colostrum 2 to 6 hours after birth.	57%	15%	66%
Provided colostrum 6 to 12 hours after birth.	43%	85%	34%
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Liquid diet type			
Fresh milk	50%	77%	50%
Waste milk	50%	23%	83%
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Weaning period			
between 60 and 90 days of age	57%	85%	50%
when calves reached 90 kg	43%	15%	50%

*Legend: Quartile 1 - 25% of farms that produced less (7/26) had an average of 264 liters. Quartile 2 - 50% of farms that had average productions (13/26) produced 681 liters per day. Quartile 3 - the most productive farms (6/26) produced 2150 liters daily.

Table 5. Health parameters from 26 dairy farms from Minas Gerais (n=20) and São Paulo (n=6) were screened to characterize different stockperson-calf interactions and their effects (negative or positive).

Farm	SCC	TBC	BW	WW	TP	BRD (%)	Diar. (%)	Om. (%)	Mo. (%)	DB (%)
1	339	11	24	90	4.8	13	25	17	≤5	≤5
2	746	10	26	90	5	60	80	0	5-10	5-10
3	187	14	20	89	5	13	38	0	≤5	≤5
4	550	26	36	78	5	0	0	0	≤5	≤5
5	750	8	33	95	5.7	0	0	0	≤5	≤5
6	580	38	37	96	5	0	40	0	10-15	10-15
7	480	42	34	77	4.7	20	20	20	10-15	10-15
8	850	18	42	83	4.8	40	40	0	10-15	10-15
9	390	35	30	75	5.1	20	20	0	≤5	≤5
10	300	16	29	82	5.3	0	0	0	≤5	≤5
11	650	5	40	91	5	40	0	0	≤5	≤5
12	650	22	37	88	5.8	0	0	0	≤5	≤5
13	180	9	33	90	4.9	20	0	0	≤5	≤5
14	150	5	32	70	5.3	40	0	0	≤5	≤5
15	400	30	35	85	5.3	0	40	0	5-10	5-10
16	190	10	28	80	5.3	0	0	0	5-10	5-10
17	430	24	37	85	4.9	0	20	0	≤5	≤5
18	800	24	31	85	4.6	20	40	0	10-15	10-15
19	330	8	36	92	5.4	0	0	0	5-10	5-10
20	350	11	38	91	5.2	20	20	0	5-10	5-10
21	650	18	39	98	5.6	0	40	0	5-10	5-10
22	200	12	35	72	5.8	0	0	0	≤5	≤5
23	685	40	38	95	5.5	20	40	20	10-15	10-15
24	380	20	36	82	4.9	0	0	0	5-10	5-10
25	300	13	38	75	5.8	0	0	20	5-10	5-10
26	530	7	40	88	5.1	27	73	40	≥15	10-15

Legend: SCC - somatic cell count ($\times 10^3$ cells/mL); TBC - Total Bacteria Counting; BW – Weight at birth; WW - Weight at weaning; TP – total protein; BRD - bovine respiratory disease; Diar - diarrhea; Om. – omphalopathies; Mo. - mortality; DB – estimated dystocic births.

Figure 1. Distribution of work system at farms according to milk yields

Figure 2. Distribution of experience time of employees working on farms according to average milk production divided into quartiles (L/day).

